

Post-Questionnaire

- 1) Please reconstruct your day as detailed as possible by listing the tasks and activities you did and the approximate duration of each task from the start of your working day to the end of your working day.

Example: 1. Checked e-mails (30 min)

2. Got a cup of coffee (10 min)

3. Online-Meeting with colleague (one hour)

4. Coding (45 min)

5. Colleague came to me and asked for coding advice (5 min) etc.

If it completely aligns with the cognitive load questionnaire, which you filled in during your working day, you may skip this question. If you however forgot to note something down during the day, please reconstruct your whole day once again. It is important to understand what you did when during the day.

General questions

- 2) How many people, approximately, did you coordinate your work with today?

No one (I did not need to coordinate my work)

2 people

3-5 people

6-14 people

15-29 people

30 or more people

- 3) Did you work remotely today?

yes

no

partly

If no: How many people were approximately in the space/office you were working in today?

1 person (just me)

2 people

3-5 people

6-14 people

15 or more people

Work satisfaction

- 4) I feel satisfied with my working day today.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

- 5) I feel satisfied with the way I was able to do my work today.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

6) What was your mood when you arrived at work today?

- Very unhappy
- Unhappy
- Neutral
- Happy
- Very Happy

7) What is your mood now at the end of your working day?

- Very unhappy
- Unhappy
- Neutral
- Happy
- Very Happy

If there is a change, what is the reason?

8) How much did each of the following challenges impact you today?

	Not at all	Very little	Somewhat	To a great extent	Not applicable
My manager					
Poorly defined goals					
Lack of team/organization vision					
Poorly qualified co-workers					
Poor team culture					
Lack of personal technical skills					
Poor software development process					
Poor engineering tools					
Poor hardware resources					
Poor collaboration tools					
Interacting with people					
Too many emails					
Too many meetings					

Too many interruptions					
Too many communication channels (email, instant messaging, etc.)					
Lack of quiet space to do work					
Finding enough time to complete my work					
Insufficient training					
Finding information of documentation					
Legacy code					
The development language, platform or stack					
Changing product requirements					
Poor software architecture					
Too many external dependencies					
Other: _____					

DevEx

Flow State

- 9) I had a significant amount of time for deep work today.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 10) How often were you interrupted to work on something else that was unplanned or suddenly requested today?
- Not at all
 - Once
 - Two to three times
 - Four to five times
 - More than five times

Feedback loops

- 11) How often did it take more than 10 minutes to obtain an answer to an internal technical question (i.e. about code, a system, or the domain you are working in) today?
- Not at all
 - Once
 - Two to three times
 - Four to five times
 - More than five times

Cognitive Load

- 12) How would you rate your overall cognitive load during work today?
- Very low
 - Low
 - Neither low nor high
 - High
 - Very high

Developer impacts

- 13) I learned new skills related to my work today.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 14) I have felt very productive today.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 15) I have been creative in my work today.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree

Perceived workload

- 16) Today I felt that the amount of work I do interferes with how well it is done. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided

- Agree
- Strongly agree

Work exhaustion

17) I feel emotionally drained from my work today. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

18) I feel used up at the end of this workday. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Questions concerning the study

- 1) Did the wristband disturb your working routine? If yes, in which situations?
- 2) Did something unusual occur during the study?
- 3) Further comments/information: _____

References

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